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Research Article

LEVEL OF URINARY INCONTINENCE IN POST-CHILDBIRTH FEMALES. A CROSS SECTIONAL SURVEY

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Article Received: August 2020**Accepted:** September 2020**Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

Background: Urinary Tract Infections and Urinary Incontinence are common among women. International Continence Society defined Urinary incontinence as involuntary loss of urine that is hygienic or social hazard and is demonstrable objectively.

Objective: The objective of the study was finding out level of urinary incontinence in post-childbirth females.

Methods: It was cross sectional survey. Females from Residential communities of Lahore were surveyed. As per convenience 390 females were contacted. Sampling technique was convenience sampling. Inclusion criteria were covering all healthy adult female population more than age of 18 years and less than that of 45 years. However, the population having known gynecology disease were excluded. Data collection tool was comprised Demographics and The Revised Urinary Incontinence Scale. Data was analyzed by using SPSS V.21.

Results: The results showed that mean and standard deviation of age= 4.0+2.74 Total Revised urinary incontinence scale (RIUS) Score=28.3+5.3, Health Related Quality of Life=7.5+1.8, Percentage of Health-Related Quality of Life= 30.20+7.29. P-Value =<0.05.

Conclusion: The findings concluded that mild level of urinary incontinence present in post-childbirth young females.

Keywords: Incontinence, Urinary Incontinence, Pregnancy, Childbirth.

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INTRODUCTION:

Urinary Tract Infections and Urinary Incontinence are common among women. International Continence Society (ICS) defined Urinary incontinence as involuntary loss of urine that is hygienic or social hazard and is demonstrable objectively [1]. Stress and urge urinary incontinence are the most common types of urinary incontinence. Stress incontinence, usually, is followed by childbirth and involves loss of support to urethral structures. It is associated with urine leakage with different activities such as sneezing, sniffing, coughing, jumping and dancing etc [2]. While urge incontinence is characterized by large amount of urine loss due uninhibited contractions of detrusor muscle [3].

Urinary incontinence can result from both urologic and non-urologic causes. Urologic causes can be delegated either bladder or urethral brokenness and may incorporate detrusor overactivity, poor bladder consistence, urethral hypermobility, or characteristic sphincter lack. Non-urologic causes may incorporate contamination, prescription or medications, mental elements, polyuria, stool impaction, and confined portability [4,5,6]. The most well-known kinds of urinary incontinence in ladies are pressure urinary incontinence and desire urinary incontinence. Ladies with the two issues have blended urinary incontinence. After menopause, estrogen creation diminishes and in certain ladies' urethral tissue will show decay with the tissue of the urethra getting to

be more fragile and thinner [7,8]. Stress urinary incontinence is brought about by loss of help of the urethra which is generally an outcome of harm to pelvic help structures because of labor. It is portrayed by spilling of little measures of pee with exercises which increment stomach weight, for example, hacking, sniffing and lifting. Also, visit practice in high-sway exercises can make athletic incontinence create. Desire urinary incontinence is brought about by uninhibited withdrawals of the detrusor muscle. It is portrayed by spilling of a lot of pee in relationship with lacking cautioning to get to the restroom in time [9-12].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study design of this survey was cross-sectional survey and sampling technique was non probability convenience sampling technique. The sample size was calculated by using this formula. $n = \frac{z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 P(1-P)}{d^2}$. Inclusion criteria were covering all healthy adult female population more than age of 18 years and less than that of 45 years. However, the population having known gynecology disease were excluded. Data collection tool was comprised Demographics and The Revised Urinary Incontinence Scale. Data was analyzed by using SPSS V.21 the descriptive statistics, frequencies and percentages were used as statistical measures. The duration of study was 06 months from February 2017 to July 2017.

RESULTS:**Table 1**

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Body Mass Index		
Underweight	221	56.7
Normal	169	43.3
Occupation		
Student	184	47.2
Employee	37	9.5
House Wife	169	43.3
Education		
Bachelors	206	52.8
Masters or above	184	47.2
Socioeconomics		
Middle Class	205	52.6
Upper Class	185	47.4
Marital Status		
Married	169	43.3
Unmarried	221	56.7

Table shows the demographical information of study population.

Graph 1

The results showed that mean and standard deviation of age, Total RIUS Score, Health Related Quality of Life, Percentage of Health-Related Quality of Life to be 28.3+5.3, 4.0+2.7, 7.5+1.8 and 30.2+7.2, respectively.

DISCUSSION:

The result showed that most of females are at risk of symptom development. All the participants were females. Although the incontinence affects the males too, but as our hypothesis focused societal issues relating females so the sample was female [13,14,15]. Middle class woman was the sample, because they were at easy access and less reluctant to share the information in this format of research surveys etc. Other observation that the group of females having moderate to severe symptoms were with common characteristics i.e. a greater number of children, more vaginal deliveries, more BMI and more age [16,17]. This was in contrary to the international findings where age, BMI and parity don't affect results to larger extent [18]. There is less literature available on finding prevalence in healthy populations. It has been investigated in specific age groups. The prevalence found previously ranged from 12% to 53%. However, these studies differ based on procedural definitions, population characteristics, material and methods of studies [19,20].

Incontinence have been found associated with racial difference, however, relationship between ethnic and incontinence is yet to understand. There is little literature on finding prevalence of urinary incontinence in Asian women [21]. A study conducted by Chan showed 4.8% of prevalence in old women from Singapore, almost equal prevalence found in elderly women in China, India and Malay. A community-based study in China showed almost 34%

of women have been [22,23] found with at least one episode of urinary incontinence as adults and about 20% been found as permanent incontinence. In another study, high prevalence of voiding symptoms found in woman of Taiwan, however, only 1.5% of women found consulting medical care for this problem [24,25]. Although the results showed most of population in safe range but there is risk of development incontinence up to clinically significant level. The one who are in safe range and ones who are not both are unaware of the facts about the incontinence so the awareness program is inevitable for this purpose.

CONCLUSION:

The findings concluded that mild level of urinary incontinence is in post-childbirth young females. Majority of females of post child birth had borderline incontinence symptoms.

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